

NECESSARY CONDITIONS AND IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *The article examines the organizational and pedagogical conditions for the use of educational and game technologies in the preparation of future teachers for innovative activities. Special attention is paid to the advantages of educational and gaming technology in the professional training of students.*

Keywords: *innovative activity, organizational-pedagogical conditions, educational and game technologies, preparation of future teachers for innovative activity.*

The reform of the modern education system includes the creation of conditions for the development of the personality of future teachers and creative self-realization. Accordingly, based on the requirements of the current period, research and development of new approaches, technologies, methods and means of preparing students studying in pedagogical higher educational institutions of our country for the profession is being intensively carried out. In recent years, the problem of using learning and game technologies as a didactic technology to strengthen the preparation of future pedagogues for innovative activities has been widely studied.

It's no secret that at the beginning of the 21st century, the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is undergoing significant changes, which are characterized by strong innovative processes and require the mass participation of teachers. UNESCO's mid-term strategy defines the need to train pedagogical personnel ready to work in a high-tech educational environment as the basis for further development of the educational system. The concept of long-term socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 emphasizes that the level of competitiveness of the modern innovative economy is determined by the quality of professional personnel and the need to introduce innovative technologies into education. Continuity of changes in the field of education determines the modern requirements of the state and society for improving the qualifications of teachers aimed at the implementation of innovative activities. In this regard, an important task of the educational staff training system is to prepare teachers for innovative activities, the result of which is the teacher's readiness for this activity.

Achieving the goals set for the higher and public education system, organizing various activities of students, raising them to be knowledgeable, polite, faithful, hardworking, well-rounded people is a pedagogue-educator, future student. is charged to the teacher. Enriching the content of lectures, practical and laboratory classes in the educational process based on new approaches, as well as improved pedagogical practice, spiritual days and hours for the professional and spiritual training of future pedagogues-educators and teachers. requires organization using programs. In order to ensure the effectiveness of higher and public education, the future teacher and pedagogue-educator must have deep pedagogical and psychological training, have clear information about the unique aspects of each student-student, and a personal plan. the following requirements must be strictly observed when creating:

able to predict emerging pedagogical problems;
for this, the future teacher and pedagogue-educator must have the ability to anticipate and eliminate problems that arise in the pedagogical process;
learn the methods of solving problems;
to be able to choose and use the most convenient methods of solving problems;
to have the ability to exert pedagogical influence on students and support them; individual approach to each student;
acquire the ability to organize public events with students;
encouraging students to read and love books.

The behavior of a teacher who can apply all these in practice will certainly be effective in the teaching process. In addition, the importance of some educational and game technologies in preparing future teachers for innovative activity processes is also high. Below, we will comment on the differences between these technologies, and it is considered necessary to pay attention to their internal appearance.

An important condition for the successful implementation of educational and game technology in the preparation of future teachers for innovative activities is the system of monitoring the educational and project activities of students.

According to the generally accepted rules of pedagogical control, it performs a number of functions: diagnostic, educational, developmental and educational. As for the proposed technology, the diagnostic function is to determine the level of readiness of students for innovative activities before starting educational and game technology, which allows to determine the tasks of the game project and helps to allocate roles. The educational function is aimed at activating the knowledge activity of students during educational and game technology, determining the level of mastery of the educational material and evaluating the results of project activities. Developmental and educational functions are aimed at developing a creative, subjective attitude to the educational process, an active life position and individual abilities in students.

In the context of training future teachers, teacher training for innovative activities is understood as interrelated, complementary and interdependent processes. That is, it is appropriate to express these processes as follows:

the teacher's mastery of innovative activities ;
taking into account the subjective experience of its implementation in an educational institution and its orientation to the professional development of the teacher. The result of this training is the formation of the teacher's readiness for innovative activities at a sufficient level (not lower than the average level).

To be more precise, its result is the formation of the teacher's readiness for innovation at a sufficient (not below average) level of teaching effectiveness with the implementation of the model of teacher preparation for innovation through the methodology of teacher preparation for innovation is provided. The model includes purposeful, meaningful, organizational-activity and reflective-evaluative blocks. This model is the basis for building an individual process of preparing a teacher for innovative activities, which considers the teacher's choice of teaching content and building his own educational direction as a goal.

In our opinion, increasing the effectiveness of the process of professional pedagogical training of pedagogues in modern socio-cultural conditions is primarily related to solving the problem of developing students of pedagogical higher education institutions as subjects of

innovative professional activity. Training of future teachers for innovative professional activity (innovative teaching of students) should work as an integrated system optimally included in the educational process of a pedagogical university through the development and introduction of appropriate technology.

Innovative training of future teachers should be aimed at their development as subjects of educational innovation and meet the basic principles of student-oriented approach and innovative pedagogical education. This is due to the subject-subject nature of the interaction between teachers and students, individualization of teaching, creating conditions for the formation of criticality and creativity in the professional thinking of future teachers, as well as the use of interactive pedagogical technologies. can also be achieved.

Management of the process of introducing educational innovations into the practice of pedagogical higher education institutions and schools can be carried out on the basis of different approaches. An attempt to systematize them can be found in the works of scientists such as V. Lazarev and M. Potashnik.

Russian scientists distinguish between administrative and participatory approaches, depending on who plays a leading role in the management of the processes of introducing educational innovations, the administration of the educational institution or the faculty.

A second important characteristic of different approaches is the type of response to change. On this basis, a distinction is made between reactive management (a type of management that involves reacting to the real situation) and anticipatory, propaedeutic management.

Based on the nature of the direction of the innovation implementation process, V. Lazarev and M. Potashnik distinguish procedural and target approaches.

A modern teacher must be ready for innovative professional activity to meet the new socio-cultural order. At the same time, according to experts, the organization of training for subjects of innovative educational activity should have its own characteristics depending on the radical level of changes. Thus, if the formation of certain competencies among teachers in the conditions of modified innovation is often enough, the formation of readiness to implement innovations in the conditions of radical innovations is possible only in the conditions of a value approach.

Summarizing the results of the scientific research of the above-mentioned scientists allows to determine the pedagogical conditions for the formation of the readiness of future teachers to manage the process of introducing educational innovations into the practice of the educational institution.

The preparation of future teachers for the implementation of educational innovations is effective if it is based on the basic rules of the program-target approach and is aimed at students' mastering the methods of developing and implementing a target program of innovative development of the educational institution.

Preparing future teachers to choose educational innovations, their implementation allows solving the identified problems, includes the development of their critical professional thinking. Preparation of future teachers to plan the process of introducing educational innovations, according to the logic of its implementation, should be aimed at developing their skills:

- development of the concept of innovative development of the educational institution;
- development of a strategic plan for the implementation of educational innovations;
- development of an operational plan.

In conclusion, it can be said that in preparing future teachers for the use of innovative educational technologies, it is necessary to familiarize them with the main provisions of the existing regulatory documents, to develop the ability of students to draw up documents necessary for the introduction of educational innovations into educational practice. All this will only be beneficial in the implementation of innovative educational activities in accordance with the institution and the rules established by them.

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